

PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article discusses the priority areas of education, physical culture and sports in the educational process.

Keywords: education system, physical culture and sport, educational process.

Introduction.

Physical culture and sports are an integral part of culture, an area of social activity, which is a set of spiritual and material values created and used by society for the purpose of physical development of a person, strengthening his health, contributing to the harmonious development of the individual. Physical culture is the broadest, collective concept, it includes all the achievements accumulated in the process of social and historical practice: the level of health, sports skills, science, works of art related to physical education, as well as material (technical) values (sports facilities, equipment).

Physical culture is understood as the totality of all the goals, tasks, means, and forms of activities inherent in a given society that contribute to the physical development and improvement of people. This includes physical education, sports [2]. In his address to the people dedicated to the 21st anniversary of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Karimov paid special attention to the healthy lifestyle of our people, especially the younger generation. The creation of an effective system of a healthy lifestyle should radically contribute to the improvement of the nation and the transition of Uzbekistan to sustainable development. A healthy

lifestyle is a prerequisite for the development of various aspects of human life, achieving active longevity and full performance of social functions, for active participation in labor, social, family, household, and leisure forms of life.

The development of physical culture and sports can be successful if the state and public administration bodies, organizations, their leaders, specialists, scientists in this field, choose the right strategy of action. If it were possible to achieve a clear understanding by the majority of people that physical activity and sports, for example, for students, are a necessary condition for the normal development of their mind and body, that the absolute majority of physical and mental diseases are somehow associated with immobility and obesity, that physical activity relieves stressful states, increases performance, reduces the level of aggression, then we would be able to not only stop the physical degradation of people, but also significantly raise their level of health. At the same time, the mere awareness of the social need for physical improvement, a physically cultured society of life, is not enough. Therefore, the country has established regulations, legal norms, and laws that stimulate and ensure the development of physical culture and mass sports at all levels: in enterprises, organizations, places of residence, recreation, families, and educational institutions. The legislation on physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan generally regulates public relations in this area, creates legal conditions for meeting the needs of the individual in harmonious development, achieving a high level of performance, forming the necessary knowledge, motor skills, physical and moral qualities of will, professional and applied training, prevention of bad habits and offenses [1].

The content of classes with university students is based on the wide use of knowledge and skills in applying the means of physical culture, using sports and

professionally applied physical training to acquire individual and collective experience of physical culture and sports activities. They teach students to regulate their motor activity, maintain the necessary level of physical and functional fitness during the training period, gain experience in improving the correction of individual physical development, learn to use the means of physical culture to organize active recreation, prevent general and occupational diseases, and prevent injuries. Students should be aware of the benefits of physical education, lead a healthy lifestyle. The purpose of physical education is to promote the training of harmoniously developed, highly qualified specialists. In the process of studying at the university on the course of physical education, the following tasks are provided for: - education of students of high moral, strong-willed and physical qualities, readiness for high-performance work; - maintaining and strengthening the health of students, promoting the correct formation and comprehensive development of the body, maintaining high performance throughout the entire period of study; - comprehensive physical training of students; - professional and applied physical training of students, taking into account the peculiarities of their future work activity; - education of students' belief in the need to regularly engage in physical culture and sports. The training process at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies for 1-2 courses is organized depending on the state of health, the level of physical development and fitness of students, their sports qualifications, as well as taking into account the conditions and nature of work of their upcoming professional activities.

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